

THE MATTERS OF ETHICS IN THE WORKS OF SHAIKH KHOVAND TOHUR.

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Annotation:

The thesis discusses the life and activities of Sheikh Khovand Tahur (XIV century), as well as the role of the scientific heritage of ancestors in the education of a mature generation, and issues of ethics in his works.?

Key words: spiritual heritage, heritage of ancestors, Sufism, teaching, Naqshbandiyya, great scholars, Sheikh Umar Bogistani, Sheikh Khovand Tohur.

Introduction. The science of Sufism is of great importance among Islamic sciences. If we take a deep look at the essence of Sufism, we will see that concepts such as philosophy, religion, sharia and ethics are combined. The main ideas of this teaching are the spiritual and moral purification of a person and the rising power of divine love.

In the 13th-14th centuries, the Mongol invaders had a negative impact on the cultural life of Movaraunnahr, but the advancement of science did not stop. Among the sciences of historiography, fiction, poetic vocabulary, and linguistics, the science of Sufism has developed widely [1]. It was during this period that the three major sects of Yassaviya, Kubroviya, and Naqshbandiyya became famous in Central Asia, and this period is called the era of Sufism sects [2].

Along with the study of the historical development and theoretical aspects of Sufism, it is also important to study the activities of great sheikhs and saints.

Scholars from Movarounnahr and Khurasan have a special role in the wide spread of Sufi views as a unified doctrine in Islamic countries and becoming an important reality in social life [3]. In particular, Sufi scholar Sheikh Khovand Tohur, who lived and worked in the XIII-XIV centuries, is considered one of the representatives who has a special place in the social-political and cultural life of the Middle Ages. His works include external (religious and secular) and internal (Sufism) sciences, and not only the medieval but also the issues of morality, which are considered to be urgent problems of today, are of great importance.

Sheikh Khawand Tohur is the son of one of the representatives of the famous sect, Sheikh Umar Baghistani. It is said that Umar Baghistani was childless, and one day

he and his wife came to Sheikh Zainiddin's mausoleum and begged God to give him a child. Soon they had a child and named him Khavandi Tohur (pure sheikh) [4].

Sheikh Khavandi Tohur received his first lesson in theology and religion from his father. According to Fakhruddin Ali Safi's "Rashahotu ainil-hayat", Sheikh Khavandi Tohur was one of the great representatives of theology and mysticism, and one of the mature mystics. He explained the doctrine of monotheism, expressions related to Sufism, and was also engaged in poetry [5].

Unlike his father, Sheikh Khovand Tohur is considered the author of several works. Ali Safi reports about this in "Rashahotu ainil-hayat" in the language of Haja Ahror Vali. It says: "Sheikh Khavandi Tohur has treatises on the Sufi order. They explained about monotheism in one of the treatises" [6].

Studying the spiritual and educational heritage of Sheikh Khavand Tohur, who is honored as a great sheikh in the Muslim world, is of great importance in raising the spirituality of young people and developing our future owners. In addition, the things they have done in their lives, the events that happened during their lives are instructive for many social problems faced by today's youth. For example, Fakhruddin Ali Safi, the author of "Rashohat" tells a story about Sheikh Umar Bogistani, the father of Sheikh Khavand Tohur. It is known that Umar Bogistani was one of the persons who mastered religious and worldly sciences, matured in Sufism, and gained respect among the people for his humility and honesty. According to the work, a man came from far away to join hands with Sheikh Umar Baghistani and become a murid. The Sheikh asked him, "Is there a mosque where you live?" he asked. When the person said yes, he said, "Do you know the rules of Islam?" he asked. "Yes," he answered. Shaykh said: "If the place of prayer is known, if the rules of prayer are known, then there is no point in your coming here, go back and engage in prayer" [7].

As can be seen from the above story, in order to acquire knowledge, be it religious or secular, a person needs to acquire knowledge not in a foreign country, but in his own country, which has all the conditions. In addition, the exemplary life of the Sheikh shows that he should stay in his country, learn and accumulate wealth, rather than leaving his homeland, parents, family, children and all his relatives alone to go to other countries, even if it is for the sake of learning or gaining wealth. is better for man. Such situations are among the vices that are widespread among today's youth.

According to Ali Safi, Shaykh Khawandi went to Turkestan to meet and learn some things from Shaykh Tenkuz, who belonged to the house of Tohur Ato Yassavi. The sheikh begins to cook, but the fire does not burn. Tenkuz Sheikh's wife is not busy with cooking and baking bread, which is a woman's job. The wood was wet and the fire would not burn. Tenkuz Sheikh's wife comes and pushes him to ashes. The Sheikh's face and beard are painted with ash. Tenkuz Sheikh endures the tyranny of his wife and does not say anything. After the having meal, Tenkuz Shaykh Shaikh Khovandi answers Tohur's problems and questions in a cheerful manner. Before leaving, Sheikh Khavandi Tohur asks why the Sheikh, having so much power, tolerates the oppression of his wife. "We made it this far because of patience!" - he said [8].

In the above-mentioned story, there is an example to prevent the destruction of young families, which is considered one of the urgent problems of today, because young people look lightly at life, impatience, trivial problems.

Sheikh Khovand Tohur's work "Risola dar masoili shari'at va tariqat" also gives very important ideas about what leads a person to perfection, first of all, the awareness of one's identity, the meaning of life and why it was created, and not to stray from the right path.

The author cites the following in order to explain this issue in depth: "There are four types of diseases that doctors cannot cure. They are istiska (jaundice), dikk (tuberculosis), juzam (leprosy) and devonagi (insanity). Sheikh Khawand explains these diseases not from a medical point of view, but from the point of view of Sharia and Tarikat.

According to the author, istiskah is an excessive desire for the world and its possessions. Dikk is the vice of selfishness, and the vice of juzom means that once someone sees a person with an incurable vice in his soul and spirit, he does not want to see him again. He talks about how the demon will go astray, the flowers will wander in the deserts, and will eventually perish like all the four evils.

In conclusion, it follows from the above statements that no person is free from bad vices such as greed, avarice, envy, grudge, and oppression, and these vices serve the devil to make a person enter the bad path and lead to destruction. A person can be cleansed from such vices, and for this, it is achieved by holding fast to the Sunnah of the Prophet. The vices listed in the work of Sheikh Khawand Tohur are among the vices that are widespread among today's youth and cause harmful consequences. It is no exaggeration to say that by reading, studying and

researching the heritage of our ancestors, informing our people about its benefits, especially our youth, we will expand the possibility of eliminating these evils.

It can be said that the approaches that incorporate issues such as humanity and morality play an important role in the upbringing of the young generation as a highly moral person. Therefore, studying and promoting the scientific heritage of ancestors in the education of the young generation, in particular, researching the sources of Sufism based on ethical issues and presenting them to the general public will bring high results in this regard. For this, first of all, we need to deeply study and deeply understand the spiritual heritage of our great scholars.

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